

ARENA Research Unit

Abstract Representations in Neural Architectures

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE
FOR SOFTWARE SYSTEMS

FIAS Frankfurt Institute
for Advanced Studies

Title: Knowledge Transfer and Outreach Report

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Knowledge Transfer and Outreach Plan

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Preamble

The research achievements of any institute or research unit cannot have their optimum impact without an active and comprehensive plan for knowledge transfer and outreach. Knowledge transfer is mainly concerned with the exchange and transfer of knowledge within the scientific community and, where appropriate, industry, through the dissemination of its results, software, and data, using various means and channels such as conferences, training programs, and publications. On the other hand, outreach focuses on the transfer of knowledge to the public and society. Therefore, the means and media should be adapted accordingly. Outreach depends mainly on communication channels such as online platforms and public lectures and events.

- The first version of the ARENA Knowledge Transfer and Outreach Plan was prepared in September 2023 and can be accessed here: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398980
- A brief report of the ARENA knowledge transfer and outreach activities from M1 to M12 can be found in the ARENA First Year Progress Report: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12743112
- A brief report of the ARENA knowledge transfer and outreach activities from M12 to M24 can be found in the ARENA Second Year Progress Report: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17077859>

In the current version of ARENA Knowledge Transfer and Outreach Plan, we have revised the plan based on our experiences over the past 24 months. Where necessary, we have modified and adjusted the activities to better meet the needs of the team.

Knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer and outreach to the scientific community and society are essential to the ARENA Research Unit. ARENA aims to use all available means to disseminate its results, to promote dialogue between science and society and to interact with scientific communities. In addition to the traditional means of disseminating its results and achievements, such as peer-reviewed publications in high-impact journals and conferences,

presentations and collaborations, ARENA will make use of broader opportunities to achieve its knowledge transfer and outreach objectives.

Considering the multidisciplinary character of ARENA, connections and contributions will be established from several perspectives. ARENA aims to systematically extend our understanding of hierarchically organised semantic knowledge in the human mind and brain along gradients of abstraction, including its learning, using AI modeling in combination with expertise in machine learning and computational neuroscience. Beyond a basic understanding of human cognition, the results of this research will be useful for future improvements in model development in the field of artificial intelligence. To this end, two strands of research will be integrated - the long tradition of cognitive science, experimental psychology, and cognitive neuroscience, and the explosive development of AI-oriented computational models in recent years.

Knowledge transfer can take place at different levels;

- At the organizational level, at Goethe University Frankfurt, the Knowledge and Technology Transfer Center¹ supports the cooperation between scientists, industry, and social communities and contributes its research expertise and the knowledge acquired by its scientists to social contexts in a variety of ways. The university Research Support² provides advice on research projects, scientific career development, and research transfer as well as support on all administrative requirements related to the life cycle of third-party funded projects.
- At the project level, ARENA projects support the cooperation among scientists and social communities and provide the possibilities of cooperation between universities and other interested parties.

ARENA believes strongly in the promotion of research, and providing training opportunities is of its highest priorities. To this end, ARENA Early Career Researchers (ECRs) will be embedded in the existing groups of the PIs, while having the opportunity to work closely with the scientific staff of other ARENA PIs' labs. For PhD students, close monitoring of progress is ensured through the establishment of interdisciplinary thesis advisory committees, to which the PhD students report on a semi-annual basis, as initially specified in a jointly signed supervision agreement. All PhD students and PostDocs are encouraged to present their research at national and international conferences. Advanced PostDocs will be supported on the basis of specific measures for their career stage, such as applying for the Goethe University's start-up funding to support the preparation of a first independent grant (Fokus Program) or for membership in the University's interdisciplinary Johanna Quandt Young Academy. ARENA ECRs will have the opportunity to invite external experts for workshops to advance their methods and expertise. ECRs are also encouraged to participate

¹ https://www.uni-frankfurt.de/38509470/Wissens_und_Technologietransfer_an_der_Goethe_Universit%C3%A4t

² https://www.uni-frankfurt.de/102672447/Research_Support

in activities beyond ARENA, such as the Young Investigator Colloquium series of the Interdisciplinary Center for Neuroscience or any other relevant mentoring program. In addition to the direct supervision provided by ARENA PIs, all project members have access to training programs of key qualifications (e.g. scientific writing) offered by the Goethe Research Academy for Early Career Researchers (GRADE)³.

Moreover, additional networking and knowledge transfer opportunities are planned through organizing events such as scientific workshops for students where ARENA members present their research and findings, Journal club, etc.

Outreach plan

The Goethe University Frankfurt Press and Communication Office⁴ supports the dissemination of research results in media, and social platforms. It is also responsible for internal communication, as well as serving as the central touchpoint for the general public and other scientific institutions. The Goethe University Frankfurt Press and Communication Office also offer a range of publication formats⁵ - UniReport, Research Frankfurt, and Goethe Spectrum - which can provide further support for knowledge communication and dissemination to the scientists as well as to the public. ARENA will benefit extensively from the support of the press and communication center to present its research outcome to a broader audience.

In addition to the comprehensive range of services offered by the central facilities of Goethe University, ARENA complements these services through its Coordination team, which next to other tasks, is responsible for public relations, communication through identified channels, such as online social platforms, informing about events, developments, and research results. A web portal⁶ is available to serve as an entry point for the public and the scientific community to retrieve information, contacts, and publications as well as to pose their questions and provide their feedback.

Interdisciplinary events and lecture series open to the public, with a mix of internal and external speakers, also coordinated by the coordination team, are planned to promote the exchange of ideas and share the results with the public. For example, ARENA aims to participate in events such as the Night of Science, where more than 70 lectures will present new findings in the natural sciences to schoolchildren, students and the interested public, as

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https://www.grade.goethe-university-frankfurt.de/54287285/Goethe_Research_Academy_for_Early_Career_Researchers#:~:text=The%20Goethe%20Research%20Academy%20for,Career%20Researchers%20at%20Goethe%20University

⁴ <https://www.puk.uni-frankfurt.de/muk?locale>

⁵ https://www.puk.uni-frankfurt.de/34459733/Die_Uni_Publikationen_im_%C3%9Cberblick

⁶ <https://neuroai-arena.github.io>

well as events organised by the Frankfurter Bürger-Universität⁷ (Frankfurt Citizens University), which aims to act as a bridge between the scientists at Goethe University and the people of the city and the region, and to create opportunities for dialogue between urban society and the university. ARENA will also organise a bi-annual series of lectures by external and internal speakers for the general public as well as for all students and colleagues.

⁷ https://www.buerger.uni-frankfurt.de/50420156/%C3%9Cber_die_Frankfurter_B%C3%BCrger_Universit%C3%A4t
